

Measuring the Immeasurable: A Framework for Organizational Ambidexterity and Intellectual Capital

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Abstract

The study focuses on the fusion of organizational ambidexterity and intellectual capital and proposes a construct to measure ambidextrous intellectual capital (AIC). We argue that ambidextrous learning is derived from intellectual capital architectures that underlie unique configurations of human, relational, and structural capital. A threefold approach was adopted to develop the AIC scale. Initially, 501 sub-dimensions of IC were identified through a literature review. In the second stage, a preliminary survey was conducted among 90 selected experts to identify the most relevant dimensions and sub-dimensions of AIC. Among the 501 identified dimensions of intellectual capital, 12 dimensions of HC, 10 dimensions of RC, and 10 dimensions of SC were selected using the mean value criterion. In the last stage, statements were generated with both dimensions of ambidexterity in mind, i.e., exploitation and exploration. The developed constructs to gauge AIC—Intellectual Capital with Organizational Ambidexterity—were reviewed by experts to determine whether the generated statements accurately captured the main idea. After incorporating experts' feedback, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted using data from 548 respondents. The results were obtained from the AIC questionnaire, which comprised 91 items. The developed questionnaire can be used to measure an organization's AIC.

Keywords - Organizational ambidexterity, Intellectual capital and ambidextrous intellectual capital

Introduction

Rapidly changing business dynamics, along with global disruptions, are compelling organizations to be ambidextrous—i.e., to balance their exploitation and exploration activities (Jansen et al., 2012). Researchers (e.g., Asiaei et al., 2018; Harris, 2000; Mubarik et al., 2019a, 2019b, 2019c) consider intellectual capital (IC) as a critical capability for acquiring organisational ambidexterity (Stewart, 1997; Pasamar et al., 2015). Transforming IC into ambidextrous IC can help firms to effectively balance exploration and exploitation activities (Mahmood & Mubarik, 2020). It implies that once the organisation has ambidextrous intellectual capital (AIC)—the capability to explore and exploit simultaneously—it can attain organisational ambidexterity (Asiaei et al., 2018). Combining IC with ambidexterity (A) to form AIC and offering a framework to gauge AIC have not yet attracted researchers' attention, as most consider ambidexterity a strategy rather than a capability (Pasamar et al., 2015). Although the term AIC has appeared several times in the extant literature, its comprehensive definition is missing. Likewise, the operationalisation of AIC is also absent from the literature. To understand the role of AIC in enhancing organisational ambidexterity and overall firm performance, it is imperative to clearly define and operationalise AIC. The present study undertakes this task by adopting a threefold approach. In the first stage, relevant literature has been reviewed to identify the dimensions and sub-dimensions of AIC. In the second stage, with the help of an expert' survey, the important sub-dimensions of AIC have been selected. In the third stage, an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was employed to develop the AIC construct. In doing so, this becomes the pioneering study that operationalizes and presents a construct to gauge the AIC. The new measure of AIC may not only be helpful for empirically examining the effect of AIC on firm performance, but also instrumental for measuring AIC levels within a firm.

Literature Review

Intellectual Capital (IC): Definitions and Dimensions

Bontis (1998); Khalique et al. (2015); Mubarik et al. (2016a, 2016b) identified three main components of IC: human capital, structural capital, and relational capital. Human capital is defined as the knowledge, skills, and abilities that individual employees exploit (Prajogo & Oke, 2016). Structural capital is the institutional knowledge used through patents, databases, structures, processes, and systems (Andrews, 2010). Finally, relational capital is defined as the knowledge rooted in interrelationship networks and their interactions among individuals (Al-Hawajreh, 2013; Mubarik et al., 2016a, 2016b). All these three elements form IC. The following section explains the dimensions and sub-dimensions of IC.

Human Capital (HC)

The literature on IC identifies HC as one of the foundations of competitive advantage in organizations (Yuksel, 2024). According to Becker (1962), HC refers to the skills, knowledge, and abilities people possess that enhance job performance. Furthermore, the concept has shifted in focus to incorporate attributes such as attitude, creativity, and problem-solving (Zafar & Yasin, 2025). Moreover, organizational HC refers to the general skills used to address a range of situations within the organization, representing knowledge and expertise acquired through

experience and training (Karadag, Sahin, & Bulut, 2025). In addition, HC is a decisive factor in creating value and enhancing organizational performance by leveraging employees' competencies and experience (Musman et al., 2025).

Structural Capital (SC)

SC comprises the organizational procedures, rituals, organizational framework, and knowledge resources that remain with the organisation and support optimal employee performance (Nurseha, Afif, & Anwar, 2024). It includes databases, trademarks, management styles, and intellectual property, which constitute an organization's experience, knowledge, and strategies (Alkalha, Jum'a, Zighan, & Abualqumboz, 2025). In addition, an effective SC structure enhances an atmosphere of innovation and education and permits procedural effectiveness (Sutrisno, Kindangen, Sendow, & Jan, 2024). Moreover, organizational capital combines internal forces, such as management philosophy and corporate culture, with SC and underscores its role in providing a foundation for HC, including innovation and organizational values (Hamdoun, Pérez-Cornejo, & Touazni, 2024). Additionally, SC is invaluable to achieving organizational performance and encompasses both tangible and intangible assets (Z. Jiang, Xu, Zhu, Liu, & Liu, 2024). Furthermore, SC plays a pivotal role in conducting business transactions and in rationalising organizational structures and procedures (He, Liu, & Lin, 2024).

Relational Capital (RC)

RC refers to the relationship an organisation has with its suppliers, customers, employees, and stakeholders, emphasizing trust and cooperation (Cosentino & Principale, 2024). It involves entries such as interactions, loyalty, and goodwill among strategic partners, as well as external factors such as brand image and customer satisfaction (Hariyono & Narsa, 2024). Although equal roles for these relationships are emphasised in numerous studies, others focus on customer capital as the key to market orientation and external relationships (Mahmood, Ali, Imran, Saleem, & Taous, 2025). Moreover, the concept of RC is occasionally extended to encompass community relationships and emphasises collaboration among all stakeholders (Odhano, Mahmood, Naqvi, & Ahmed, 2025). In this study, the term relational capital refers to the relationships the firm has with all its stakeholders.

Organizational Ambidexterity (OA)

OA is defined by Duncan (1976) and March (1991) as the capacity of organizations to balance two separate learning processes: exploration (innovation, experimentation) and exploitation (efficiency, refinement) (Pietsch, Aydin, Montecinos, & Bellibaş, 2025). The ability of organizations to balance these activities is the only way to emerge successful, since OA have been shown to succeed more often than their non-ambidextrous counterparts (Shi, Van Toorn, & McEwan, 2024). Such organisations can compete effectively while simultaneously developing new products and services (Restuputri, Masudin, Septira, Govindan, & Widayat, 2024). The notion intertwines with the dynamic capabilities, underscoring that the ability to attain ambidexterity is key to an organization's success (Sarmiento et al., 2024). Thus, strategic decision-making, structural differentiation, and allocation of resources between exploration

and exploitation activities are the main elements of effective ambidexterity (Fernández-Pérez de la Lastra & Sánchez-Gardey, 2024).

Ambidextrous Organizations (AO)

AOs are very important for competitive advantage in the current dynamic world, where agility and innovation are key to stability (Jain, Badra, & Vichore, 2024). In addition, AO facilitates lifelong learning to develop dynamic competencies and strategic renewal (AlSaied & Alkhoraif, 2024). Moreover, the main advantages of ambidexterity include greater capacity to make strategic choices, the development of unique competencies, and the avoidance of inflexibility in core competencies (Mahmood, Imran, Ali, Khan, & Rashid, 2025). Additionally, organizations need to strike a balance between exploration, which seeks to find new opportunities, and exploitation, which seeks to enrich matching knowledge (Narayanan & Altay, 2024). Furthermore, it has been shown that individuals who adopt both strategies simultaneously are more innovative and effective than those who adopt either strategy alone (Kandoth & Shekhar, 2025). Nonetheless, achieving balance is difficult because exploration and exploitation compete for available resources (Moreno-Luzon, Gil-Marques, Lloria, & Salas-Vallina, 2024).

Ambidextrous Intellectual Capital (AIC)

Ambidextrous organizations combine exploration and exploitation to increase intellectual capital (AIC) (Hayaeian & Hesarzadeh, 2024). Exploration is the act of increasing knowledge in new fields, whereas exploitation is the act of increasing knowledge in old fields (Zahid, Zhang, Shahzad, Junaid, & Shrivastava, 2024). Additionally, research indicates that achieving effective ambidexterity requires a delicate balance between the two modes, with IC playing a significant role (Y. Jiang, Guo, He, & Chen, 2025). According to Mahmood et al. (2025), ambidexterity can be developed through certain resource architectures that combine different forms of knowledge and expertise, enabling both exploitation and exploration. Furthermore, the literature indicates that both types of human capital are necessary for successful organizational development, and that the relationship between social and structural capital is interdependent (Ortiz-Regalado & Guevara, 2024).

Human Capital: Specialists versus Generalists

Human resource management practices, based on recruitment, placement, and retention mechanisms, are essential for achieving competitive advantage (Takahashi, 2025). HC is either a generalist or a specialist. Generalist human capital entails general training of employees with multi-skills, whereas specialist HC entails comprehensive domain knowledge through specialized training (Aziegbe-Esho, 2025). The decision to be a generalist or a specialist affects learning and the application of knowledge in organizations (Gruber, Dencker, & Nikiforou, 2024). The specialist HC will face the issue of functional bias and therefore lack the flexibility to absorb external skills that are not part of their field. In contrast, generalists can adjust and draw on diverse expertise across fields, providing different insights crucial to the performance and retention mechanisms of organizations (Lu, Wan, & Xu, 2025).

Relational Capital: Cooperative Versus Entrepreneurial

The RC is split into two categories, namely cooperative and entrepreneurial (Martínez-López, Fernández-Barcala, González-Díaz, & Iliopoulos, 2025). In addition, cooperative RC has dense networks, shared knowledge, job-based compensation, and set norms, whereas the entrepreneurial RC is more flexible and resilient and bases trust development on personal experience (Badraoui, Saikouk, & Fattam, 2025; Paoloni, De Andreis, & Papa, 2024). Furthermore, researchers identify three elements of relational capital: affect (expectations and trust), structure (relationships among individuals), and cognition (shared meaning). Additionally, cooperative RC acts as a close social network with high levels of trust that enhances effective knowledge acquisition, whereas entrepreneurial relational capital serves as a weaker social network that prevents exploitation inefficiency and facilitates exploratory learning (Cosentino & Principale, 2024; OYEKU, ADEJUWON, & OYEKU, 2025). Moreover, the role of RC in organizational behaviour and its impact on knowledge sharing and collaboration (Rivera, Rivera-González, Escamilla-García, & Carrillo Gamboa, 2025).

Structural Capital: Organic Versus Mechanistic

As explained by Kang and Snell (2009), SC is categorized into two types: mechanistic and organic. The organization's rules and norms guide the mechanistic SC and, therefore, enable performance appraisal and knowledge accumulation through cause-and-effect relationships (Annamalah et al., 2023). Moreover, organic SC promotes flexibility, creativity, and individual autonomy within a less rigid organizational culture, thereby fostering proactive learning (S. Lee & Han, 2024). This twin-level structure affects knowledge integration: mechanistic capital underpins standardized processes and exploitation learning, whereas organic capital enables exploration and the making of innovative decisions (Kim, 2025). All these forms influence an organization's capacity to evolve and survive through institutionalized knowledge and cultural structures (C.-C. Lee, Yeh, Yu, & Luo, 2023).

Methodology

Research Approach

We adopted a three-fold approach for developing the construct of AIC as explained below:

Identification- The literature review was conducted at the initial level to determine the dimensions and sub-dimensions of IC. Similarly, the literature on organizational ambidexterity was reviewed to identify its critical dimensions.

Selection- The surveys used in this stage were used to select the relevant dimensions and sub-dimensions of IC, with expert help, as outlined below.

- **Sampling Experts**

The second stage involved expert sampling, a sub-case of purposive sampling, in which experts were selected.

- **Data Collection from Experts**

Experts were used to collect data via a three-point scale questionnaire, where 1 = not important, 2 = somewhat important, and 3 = very important. Part 1 of the questionnaire included 197 possible dimensions of human capital, 147 of relational capital, and 157 of structural capital, all chosen based on the empirical literature. 501 sub-dimensions were summarized in Part 2 of the questionnaire. Slight modifications were made based on the experts' feedback, and the questionnaire was distributed to them via email.

- **Selection Criteria**

The criteria used to choose the dimensions were borrowed from the computation of the mean values of the separate dimensions (Mahmood, Mubarik, Islam, & Naghavi, 2021). (Mubarik et al., 2019) affirms that it is calculated by multiplying each respondent's percentage by their value and summing the products. As an illustration, when 60 % of the respondents ranked Variable A as not important, 30 % somewhat important and 10 % very important, the mean value will be = $[(60\% \times 1) + (30\% \times 2) + (10\% \times 3)]$, where the number 3, 2 and 1 will be used to refer to important, somewhat important and not important respectively. The cut-off criteria were set to the average of the minimum and maximum means.

$$\text{Mean Value} = \% \text{Not Important} (1) + \% \text{Somewhat Important} (2) + \% \text{Important} (3) \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Cut-off} = (\text{Minimum mean value} + \text{Maximum Mean Value})/2 \quad (2)$$

Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA)

The chosen dimensions and sub-dimensions were then transformed into the statement 'knowing in view' of the IC and organizational ambidexterity. The principal component method was used to identify the number of factors, based on data collected from 300 firm respondents.

Findings

The entire scale development has been separated into three large sections. The first is defining the pertinent dimensions and sub-dimensions of ambidextrous intellectual capital. The second one is the choice of appropriate AIC dimensions. The third is the item creation to operationalize the dimensions and sub-dimensions for an exploratory factor analysis (EFA) in support of the final construct decision. After that, the following 11 keywords were identified to search for relevant studies on intellectual capital and organizational ambidexterity.

Identification - A review of the quantitative studies conducted from 1958 to 2020 was the first step. Following the review of the studies, we identified the HC, RC, and SC dimensions. As these tables show, every dimension of IC has been reflected in various qualitative and quantitative factors. However, not all aspects might matter in measuring ambidextrous intellectual capital. Therefore, to choose the most applicable dimensions of HC, SC, and RC, we used a preliminary survey, as explained in the previous section.

Selection - An initial survey was conducted using a questionnaire developed from 03 scales (01 = not important, 3 = important). It mailed questionnaires to 90 selected professionals. The average value and the cut-off values were calculated as described in the preceding section. The

HC, relational capital, and structural capital had cutoff criteria of 2.5, 2.48, and 2.53, respectively, resulting from averaging the maximum and minimum mean values. Out of the list of 501 dimensions of IC that have been identified, 10 dimensions of HC, 9 dimensions of RC and 9 dimensions of structural capital have been chosen as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Selected sub-dimensions of IC

Human capital	Structural capital	Relational capital
Education	Intellectual property rights	Relationships with customers
Experience	Research and development	Customer service
Expertise	Business process re-engineering	Relationships with suppliers
Skills	Working systems	Goodwill
Training	Brand and trademark reputation	Distribution channels
Creativity	Databases	Cooperation with universities and research institutes
Attitudes	Portfolio management	Strategic alliance
Abilities	Internal management systems	Relationships with stakeholders
Health	Organizational structure	Internal relationship management
Capability		

Exploratory Factor Analysis

Generation of Items

Once the most viable IC dimensions had been selected, the organizational ambidexterity consideration was followed by the generation of statements for each item based on its connection to ambidexterity. The statements were created with consideration of the integration of both dimensions of ambidexterity, i.e., exploitation and exploration. Hence, every statement measures the effectiveness of that dimension in both exploration and exploitation perspectives. By doing this, we have developed statements for each of the AHC, ASC, and ARC dimensions. As such, 248 items were gleaned to make 96 items to represent AIC (80 items to represent ARC and 72 items to represent ASC). The formulated constructs to measure ambidextrous intellectual capital, that is, Intelligent Capital with Organizational Ambidexterity, were reviewed by professionals to determine whether the statements generated capture the primary concept. We submitted the construct to 30 professionals. The professionals picked then were from industry, academia, and institutions to obtain a diverse opinion. The professionals recommended removing certain items because they overlapped with other items. Following the incorporation of the experts' feedback, 192 items were retained to offer AIC (72 items of AHC, 60 items of ARC, and 60 items of ASC). Data were collected by the final version of the construct on 548 respondents.

PCA Findings

The ambidextrous Intellectual capital was designed to be exploratory factor-analysed with a starting set of 192 items. The exploratory factor analysis was conducted using the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) method in SPSS version 22. The suitability of EFA for the data

was assessed before the formal application. The correlations between the items were greater than 0.3 for most. The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) value was 0.889, well above the recommended threshold of 0.6 (Kaiser and Rice, 1974). Also, the Bartlett test of sphericity was significant, indicating that the correlation matrix is factorable (Bartlett, 1954).

In the case of ambidextrous human capital (AHC), the principal component analysis was used to extract 33 factors with Eigenvalues exceeding 1. The overall data explained variance was 59.03%. Varimax rotation was used to enhance the interpretability of the constructs. The resultant structure was a simple one, loading the items on the construct in question. The elements drawn are identified as related to the former studies.

The constructs of ambidextrous relational capital (ARC) demonstrated a principal components analysis with four components, each with an eigenvalue greater than 1, which explained 26.3%, 35.4%, 41.4%, 46.8%, 51.1%, 54.5%, 57.0%, 59.5%, and 61.4% of the variance, respectively. The Cattell (1966) screen test was used to identify 09 components for further investigation. The results of the parallel analysis were also used to support the decision, as only 9 components had eigenvalues greater than the corresponding criterion values when compared with a randomly generated data matrix of the same size (variables 60 x 549 respondents). Varimax rotation was used to aid in the interpretation of these nine components. The rotated solution indicated the existence of a simple solution, and all 9 components had a few strong loadings. The 9-component solution explained 61.40 per cent of the variance. Of the 9 components selected, 26 items were retained. Tables 2, 3, and 4 show the explanatory power of factors.

In ambidextrous structural capital (ASC), 9 factors with Eigenvalues greater than 1 were obtained in the principal components analysis. The overall amount of variation in the data explicated was 64.63%. Varimax rotation was used to enhance the interpretability of the constructs derived from the drawing. The resulting structure showed a basic structure loading only the 26 items on the construct in question. The components to be drawn are consistent with past studies. Appendix 1 presents the final AIC construct, composed of 91 items.

Table 2 Factor-wise explanatory power (Ambidextrous Human Capital-AHC)

	Education	Experience	Skills	Trainings	Capabilities	Expertise	Abilities	Attitude	Creativity	Health
Eigen Value	14.8	11.4	4.1	2.3	2.2	1.7	1.6	1.52	1.3	1.291
Variance Extracted	13	91	92	27	10	08	22	4	25	
	20.5	15.9	5.8	3.2	3.0	2.3	2.2	2.11	1.8	1.794
	74	60	22	32	70	73	53	7	40	
Cumulative Variance Extracted	20.5	36.5	42.3	45.5	48.6	51.0	53.2	55.4	57.2	59.033
	74	34	56	87	57	30	83	00	39	

Table 3 Factor-wise explanatory power of ambidextrous relational capital (ARC)

	Relationship with suppliers	Relationship with customer	Good will	Customer service	Strategic alliance	Distribution channels	Cooperation with Universities and Research Institutes	Relationship with Stakeholders	Internal Relationship Management
Eigen value	15.806	5.488	3.601	3.2	2.605	2.001	1.538	1.322	1.285
Variance extracted	26.343	9.147	6.001	5.333	4.342	3.335	2.563	2.203	2.141
CVE	26.343	35.49	41.491	46.824	51.166	54.501	57.064	59.267	61.408

CVE Stands for Cumulative Variance Extracted

Table 4: Factor-wise Explanatory Power (Ambidextrous Structural Capital-ASC)

	Intellectual Property Rights	DB	Business Process Reengineering	WS	Brand and trademark reputation	R&D	Internal management Systems	OS	Portfolio management
Eigen Value	19.09	5.11	3.67	3.31	2.02	1.80	1.40	1.24	1.13
Variance Extracted	31.82	8.52	6.12	5.52	3.36	3.00	2.33	2.06	1.88
Cumulative Variance Extracted	31.82	40.35	46.47	51.99	55.35	58.36	60.69	62.75	64.63

Conclusion and Implications

The researchers and policymakers believe that a balance between exploration (innovation) and exploitation (productivity) can improve a firm's performance. This equilibrium at the firm level can be achieved by imbuing ambidexterity into the intellectual capital. If intellectual capital is ambidextrous, it can assist organizations in achieving organizational ambidexterity. Though anecdotal support is provided for this fact, there is no literature on studies measuring ambidextrous intellectual capital (AIC). Here, the super-objective of this chapter was to operationalize and develop a holistic measure of AIC. The study developed a 91-item AIC

scale using a three-pronged approach that captures both qualitative and quantitative facets of AIC. The scale developed would be used to investigate the effects of AIC on various aspects of firm performance. On the same note, the developed scale could be applied to analyse the level of AIC within an organization. In addition, the research attracts another insightful conclusion on how to create AIC.

To start with, AIC is an organization's ability to maintain steady organizational performance. It entails intentional actions by the organization to actualise the AIC by reorganising its strategies. Organizations ought to build AIC around sequential, structural, and contextual ambidexterity across customers, business, and corporate strategies. Ambidextrous skills are often complex to achieve, involving a variety of strategic elements.

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